

D8.3 REPORT ON APPLIED NLP NAMED ENTITY RECOGNITION

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Project Acronym: CLS INFRA

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The following report documents the work of Work Package 8 in the CLS Infrastructure Project. The general goals of this work package are to increase the ease of access and application to NLP tools, including for less-well-resourced languages, as well as their standardization.

The report is organized as follows: a generation explanation of named entity recognition tasks, technical boundaries, challenges for literary scholar (and or those working with unstructured texts) and thus proposed tools for these tasks. This includes machine learning pipeline for automatically extracting pre-defined mentions of known objects, such as people, places or organizations to generative AI solutions and in multiple languages applicable to a wide set of scholars. These tools integrate work in both WP 6 and 7 which facilitates integration of the pipeline from data preparation, programmable corpora, to analysis and back.

Named Entity Recognition (NER) is a task of natural language processing (NLP). NER seeks to identify and classify named entities - real-world objects or concepts, such as people, places, organizations, locations, dates, etc... This facilitates scholars to with lists of said entities to further contextualize an unstructured text.

NER systems can take on a number of technical models including: (1) rule-based systems – where a set of boundaries or rules are made to identify named entities (e.g. Capital letters suggesting proper nouns); (2) machine learning for pattern recognition of labeled data, (3) deep learning that includes pattern recognition with more complex textual features; and (4) more recently generative AI approaches (e.g. LLMs).

There remain a number of challenges that include but are not limited to contextual features of the text that infer ambiguity (e.g. where person names could also be locations or organizations); spelling variations, as well as limitations based on language where grammar and spelling rules differ. Rule based and machine learning systems are also in need of labeled/annotated gold standard data for training and/or evaluation. For literary scholars there also remains technical challenges in implementing off-the-shelf techniques needing sufficient knowledge of python or C++, etc... In an effort to overcome a number of these challenges we have developed a number of tools.

First we developed a set of tools that include Jupyter notebooks, Nametagger 1-3 and related models and Cadet. Each of these tools are detailed here below.

The Jupyter notebooks cater to scholars who want to perform aspect/named entity recognition in these three common scenarios for CLS: (1) you have no gold standard data available, (2) you have limited gold standard data available (only for evaluation), and (3) you have enough gold standard data available for training and evaluation. In these three scenarios, they implement **off-the-shelf models** (using packages such as Flair and spaCy), **discriminative models** (using HuggingFace model hub for training) and, at the time of writing more experimental **generative**

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models (using Mixtral AI and GPT4ALL). Each notebook is a more educational and step-wise version of the code which was used for research purposes (Dejaeghere et al., 2024).

All notebooks show outline how one can implement a plain text corpus, transform it into a Pandas DataFrame and output an entity/aspect column which can then be exported as a .csv-file. A number of approaches to NER are explored on an in-house annotated corpus of travel literature, which can easily be accessed and played around with through GitHub. The following notebooks were developed (each detailed here below):

1. Information extraction notebooks (NER)
 - a. NER with spaCy (OTS + DISCR)
 - b. NER with Flair (OTS + DISCR)
 - c. NER with Mixtral with zero-shot and in-context learning (GEN)
 - d. NER with Mixtral with chain of thought (GEN)
 - e. NER with GPT4ALL (GEN)
2. Common NLP processes for NER
 - a. Bootstrapping entities with an off-the-shelf model for post-correction.
 - b. Transform NER annotations to IOB-labels for evaluation.
 - c. Perform statistical tests to find significant differences between groups.

Each notebook details the background knowledge on NLP which you need to understand and adapt the code, details the steps and mentions some of the limitations and advantages of each approach. Additionally, we point users to other sources on the subject and packages to try.

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Figure 1: overview of the Jupyter Notebooks

We have also developed a number of tools for developing your own model in any language. These are the tools of Name tagger 1 - 3. This tool marks named entities in your texts. Nametagger 2 builds on this system for nested named entities. For instance, two entities can be recognized in *Humboldt University*: institution (the whole string) and surname (*Humboldt*). And Nametagger 3 which specifically is a tool for nested Czech named entities for example that two entities can be recognized in *Humboldt University*: institution (the whole string) and surname (*Humboldt*). The currently available models are Czech and “multilingual”. The multilingual model is trained on CoNLL data of the following languages

Finally for NLP and thus NER tasks of less resourced languages we have developed the tool Cadet. Cadet facilitates the creation and generation of new language models for spaCy. spaCy supports many languages, but not all, and Cadet helps you create a new language object and associate various assets with it, including sample sentences, tokenization rules, lemma lookup tables, stop words etc. This includes a batch annotation feature which allows you to annotate the most frequent tokens in your corpus quickly before exporting the corpus for more detailed annotation work in Inception. With a annotated your text corpus one can train a number of NLP models.

Jupyter Notebooks for NER in CLS

The Jupyter notebooks for NER developed, are detailed here as separate notebooks and models including: spaCy, Flair, Mixtral with zero-shot and in-context learning, Mixtral with chain of thought, GPT4ALL, as well as additional common NLP processes for NER.

NER with spaCy (OTS + DISCR)

NER with Flair (OTS + DISCR)

Version

Versioning depends on the Python packages used in the Jupyter Notebooks. At the time of writing, these are the versions of the most important installed dependencies:

- flair 0.15.0
 - Dkpro-cassis 0.9.1
 - Spacy 3.7.6
 - langchain 0.3.14
 - langchain_community 0.3.14
 - langchain_core 0.3.29
 - langchain_text_splitters NA
 - nervaluate NA
 - numpy 1.26.4
 - pandas 2.2.2
 - pydantic 2.10.5
 - pydantic_core 2.27.2
 - sklearn 1.6.0
 - torch 2.5.1+cu121
 - transformers 4.47.1
 - gpt4all NA
-
- IPython 7.34.0
 - jupyter_client 6.1.12
 - jupyter_core 5.7.2
 - notebook 6.5.5
-
- Python 3.11.11

Version Date

20/01/2025

Which Operating Systems does it work on?

- Windows
- Unix
- MacOS
- Linux

Licence

- Fully free (do you need the exact name, e. g. *CC-BY*? Add it into parentheses!)
- Freemium (free only for a limited time or with a limited capacity or functionality)

Distribution

- Cloud service
- Library for Python
- Local

Where to download, how to install, documentation, user guides

- <https://github.com/GhentCDH/CLSinfra/tree/main> all information regarding the literary-historical annotations of the travel literature dataset, the Python packages, and the rationale behind the creation of the notebooks can be found on our GitHub which gets updated regularly.

User interface

- GUI (Jupyter Notebook)
- API REST (HuggingFace API)

Docker instance

- Yes

How does the tool process your text?

- Automatically adds some labels (labels) to your texts.

Does the tool allow you to export the results?

- Yes, the tool shows you how to apply information extraction and export the results as a .csv-file.

Is this tool a statistical model (or a set thereof)?

- No, however, the Notebooks use off-the-shelf statistical models, and shows you how to adapt them to your purpose.

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Does this tool include statistical models? (Irrelevant, erase if this is a statistical model)

- Yes

Can you easily train and use your own statistical model with this tool ?

- Yes

XML-TEI compatibility

- The tool does not support XML-TEI at all.

How is an input document to be structured for the tool?

- The Notebooks showcase how to upload .txt-input documents and/or .csv-files.

Methods and features

We use a tool to solve a task. The tool is approaching this task with methods to provide some features or compute values of some metrics for the given text. Features typically enrich the input text (either in-line or stand-off) with labels or filter the text according to a query. Assigned labels typically belong to a given tagset (e. g. Universal Dependencies or Penn Treebank) or/and pertain to a formalism such as HPSG or minimalist syntax). Filters typically pertain to a query language (also a formalism).

Quick orientation for contributors	Task (what you want to achieve with that method)	Method (usually more generic than task)	Features/ Metric/ Formalism, Tagset
NLP	Extract entities such as persons, dates, and locations	Named Entity Recognition	Features: Labels on recognized entities

Which human languages does the tool support (as of February 2023)?

The Notebooks show how to adapt the tools to Dutch, French, English and German using a toy literary-historical dataset, but to what languages it can be adapted depends on the dependencies (e.g.: spacy, Flair, Mixtral, ...).

Language	Variety (geographical, or temporal if not modern)
Dutch (not Flemish)	

English	
Flemish (not Dutch)	
French	
German	

Which other tools from this list does it integrate?

- spaCy
- Flair

What can this tool do for you?

Using this Notebook with spaCy and Flair scholars can perform aspect/named entity recognition using an off-the-shelf model. The notebook shows you how to start from a plain text corpus, transform it into a Pandas DataFrame and output an entity/aspect column which can then be exported as a .csv-file. This details the following processes: NER with spaCy (OTS + DISCR) and Flair.

Aspect_spacy

Using our labeled travelogues data as a showcase, we show you the following functionalities of the [spaCy package](#):

1. Generate off-the-shelf entities for your corpus using spaCy's models (EN, FR, NL, GER).
2. Generate off-the shelf entities for your corpus and enrich with rules ([EntityRuler](#)).
3. Generate zero-shot entities for your corpus with spaCy's [GliNER](#).
4. Train and save a model on top of spaCy's off-the-shelf models.

Aspect_flair

Using our labeled travelogues as a showcase, we show you the following functionalities of the [Flair package](#):

1. Generate off-the-shelf entities for your corpus using [Flair's off-the-shelf models \(EN, FR, NL, GER\)](#).
2. Evaluate the results of your tagger on a small test set.
3. Generate zero-shot entities for your corpus using Flair's [TARSTAGGER](#).
4. Generate few-shot entities for your corpus by fine-tuning Flair's TARSTAGGER.
5. Create your own SequenceTagger on top of TARSTAGGER.

Papers

D8.3 REPORT ON APPLIED NLP NAMED ENTITY RECOGNITION

- Anand, Y., Nussbaum, Z., Treat, A., Miller, A., Guo, R., Schmidt, B., Community, G., Duderstadt, B., Mulyar, A., 2023. GPT4All: An Ecosystem of Open Source Compressed Language Models. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2311.04931>
- Dejaeghere, T., Singh, P., Lefever, E., Birkholz, J., 2024. Exploring Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis Methodologies for Literary-Historical Research Purposes, in: Sprugnoli, R., Passarotti, M. (Eds.), Proceedings of the Third Workshop on Language Technologies for Historical and Ancient Languages (LT4HALA) @ LREC-COLING-2024. ELRA and ICCL, Torino, Italia, pp. 129–143.
- Klie, J.-C., Bugert, M., Boullosa, B., de Castilho, R.E., Gurevych, I., 2018. The INCEpTION Platform: Machine-Assisted and Knowledge-Oriented Interactive Annotation, in: Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Computational Linguistics: System Demonstrations. Association for Computational Linguistics, Santa Fe, USA, pp. 5–9.

NER with Mixtral with zero-shot and in-context learning (GEN)**NER with Mixtral with chain of thought (GEN)****Version**

Versioning depends on the Python packages used in the Jupyter Notebooks. At the time of writing, these are the versions of the most important installed dependencies:

- langchain 0.3.14
- langchain_community 0.3.14
- langchain_core 0.3.29
- langchain_text_splitters NA
- nervaluate NA
- numpy 1.26.4
- pandas 2.2.2
- pydantic 2.10.5
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- torch 2.5.1+cu121
- transformers 4.47.1

- IPython 7.34.0
- jupyter_client 6.1.12
- jupyter_core 5.7.2
- notebook 6.5.5

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- If accessed through the API, you need an API key to make calls and the number of calls which can be made is limited unless you subscribe to a payment plan.

Distribution

- Cloud service

Where to download, how to install, documentation, user guides

- <https://github.com/GhentCDH/CLSinfra/tree/main> all information regarding the literary-historical annotations of the travel literature dataset, the Python packages, and the rationale behind the creation of the notebooks can be found on our GitHub which gets updated regularly.

User interface

- GUI (Jupyter Notebook)
- API REST (HuggingFace API)

Docker instance

- Yes

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Does this tool include statistical models? (Irrelevant, erase if this is a statistical model)

- Yes

Can you easily train and use your own statistical model with this tool ?

- No

XML-TEI compatibility

- The tool does not support XML-TEI at all.

How is an input document to be structured for the tool?

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Methods and features

Quick orientation for contributors	Task (what you want to achieve with that method)	Method (usually more generic than task)	Features/ Metric/ Formalism, Tagset
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Language	Variety (geographical, or temporal if not modern)
Dutch (not Flemish)	
English	
Flemish (not Dutch)	
French	
German	

Which other tools from this list does it integrate?

- mistralai/Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1 LLM

What can this tool do for you?

Using this Notebook made with the mistralai/Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1 model, scholars can perform aspect/named entity recognition using a generative models The notebook shows you how to start from a plain text corpus, transform it into a Pandas DataFrame and output an entity/aspect column which can then be exported as a .csv-file. This details the following processes: NER with Mixtral with zero-shot and in-context learning (GEN) and NER with Mixtral with chain of thought (GEN).

Aspect_mixtral

This notebook shows you how to use the [LangChain](#) framework in combination with Mistral's Large Language Model [Mixtral-8x7b](#) to perform aspect/named entity recognition in English, French, German and Dutch:

1. Perform zero-shot aspect/named entity recognition, validate and parse the output as JSON.
2. Perform few-shot aspect/named entity recognition, validate and parse the output as JSON.
3. Calculate evaluation metrics for the results.

The output is parsed as JSON using the Python package [Pydantic](#) to transform partial JSON outputs to a valid JSON object.

CoT_mixtral

This notebook shows you how to use the Langchain framework in combination with Mistral's LLM [Mixtral-8x7b](#) to perform aspect/named entity recognition through a chain of thought approach. This is an adaptation of the `Aspect_mixtral` notebook.

1. Perform zero-shot aspect/named entity recognition through a chain of thought prompt and parse the output as JSON.
2. Perform few-shot aspect/named entity recognition through a chain of thought prompt and parse the output as JSON.

Papers

- Anand, Y., Nussbaum, Z., Treat, A., Miller, A., Guo, R., Schmidt, B., Community, G., Duderstadt, B., Mulyar, A., 2023. GPT4All: An Ecosystem of Open Source Compressed Language Models. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2311.04931>
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NER with GPT4ALL

Version

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- pandas 2.2.2
- gpt4all NA

- IPython 7.34.0
- jupyter_client 6.1.12
- jupyter_core 5.7.2
- notebook 6.5.5

- Python 3.11.11

Version Date

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- GUI (Jupyter Notebook)

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- Yes

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The Notebooks show how to adapt the tools to Dutch, French, English and German using a toy literary-historical dataset, but to what languages it can be adapted depends on the dependencies (e.g.: spacy, Flair, Mixtral, ...).

Language	Variety (geographical, or temporal if not modern)
Dutch (not Flemish)	
English	
Flemish (not Dutch)	
French	
German	

Which other tools from this list does it integrate?

- GPT4ALL

What can this tool do for you?

Using this Notebook made with GPT4ALL, scholars can perform aspect/named entity recognition using a generative models. The notebook shows you how to start from a plain text corpus, transform it into a Pandas DataFrame and output an entity/aspect column which can then be exported as a .csv-file. This details the following processes: NER with GPT4ALL (GEN).

NER_LLM

This notebook shows you how to use the GPT4ALL framework to perform aspect/named entity recognition in English, French, German and Dutch using multiple models available in the [GPT4ALL tool suite](#) (Anand et al., 2023). This is open-source software which aims to democratize LLM access by offering compressed versions of models in the 3-13B parameter

range for use on commodity hardware through its Python bindings, as well as a no-code user interface, which can be of use for low-resource DH projects.

The models tested in our research approach included **mistral-7b-instruct-v0.1.Q4_0.gguf**, **nous-hermes-llama2-13b.Q4_0.gguf** and **Meta-Llama-3-8B-Instruct.Q4_0.gguf**, and we tested and compared a range of prompting methodologies across centuries and languages available in our dataset as depicted in Figure 2. However, models can of course be easily swapped out for other models available in the GPT4ALL tool suite, and prompts can just as easily be adapted within the Jupyter Notebook.

1. Create a prompt chain using GPT4ALL and parse the output as JSON.

Figure 2: overview of prompting methodologies

Papers

- Anand, Y., Nussbaum, Z., Treat, A., Miller, A., Guo, R., Schmidt, B., Community, G., Duderstadt, B., Mulyar, A., 2023. GPT4All: An Ecosystem of Open Source Compressed Language Models. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2311.04931>
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Common NLP processes for NER

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- nervaluate NA
- matplotlib 3.10.0
- pandas 2.2.2
- scipy 1.13.1
- seaborn 0.13.2
- statsmodels 0.14.4

- IPython 7.34.0
- jupyter_client 6.1.12
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Can you easily train and use your own statistical model with this tool ?

- No

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Methods and features

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Language	Variety (geographical, or temporal if not modern)
Dutch (not Flemish)	
English	
Flemish (not Dutch)	
French	
German	

Which other tools from this list does it integrate?

- spaCy

What can this tool do for you?

This notebook caters to scholars who want to perform a number of common NLP processes for NER. This includes: (1) Bootstrapping entities with an off-the-shelf model for post-correction; (2) Transforming NER annotations to IOB-labels for evaluation; (3) Perform statistical tests to find significant differences between groups.

Bootstrapping

This notebook shows you how to bootstrap your corpus. It uses spaCy's off-the-shelf NER model, and shows you how to integrate the results in XMI XML. This is the input format of the annotation platform Inception (Klie et al., 2018), and allows you to post-correct entities instead of annotating your texts from scratch. This notebook can be adapted with other tools to bootstrap data for Inception.

Annotations to IOB-labels

This language-agnostic notebook shows you how to transform your annotations to an IOB-format. It takes the sentence/chunk and the entity text column as an input, and adds a new column to your DataFrame with the IOB-annotations in a list. We do this to be able to apply span evaluation and calculate F1-scores.

Sentence	Entity text	Entity category	IOB
I am in Rome	Rome	LOCATION	[O, O, O, B-LOCATION]

Figure 3: example of NER labels to IOB

Statistical analysis

This Notebook provides code to find significant differences in model performance across groups (e.g.: in our case, we used it to calculate the performance of prompts across centuries and entity category labels).

- **Normality Test:** Uses the Shapiro-Wilk test to assess whether the data for each metric is normally distributed within each group.
- **ANOVA Test:** If all groups are normal, performs a one-way ANOVA to check for significant differences between group means.
- **Post Hoc Analysis:** If ANOVA finds significant differences, performs Tukey's test for pairwise comparisons.
- **Non-parametric Test:** If the normality assumption fails, uses the Kruskal-Wallis test to detect differences between groups.
- **Post Hoc for Non-parametric Data:** If Kruskal-Wallis finds significant differences, performs pairwise Mann-Whitney U tests.

The Notebook creates a results file summarizing normality tests, ANOVA/Kruskal-Wallis tests, and post hoc comparisons for the dataset at hand.

Papers

- Anand, Y., Nussbaum, Z., Treat, A., Miller, A., Guo, R., Schmidt, B., Community, G., Duderstadt, B., Mulyar, A., 2023. GPT4All: An Ecosystem of Open Source Compressed Language Models. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2311.04931>
- Dejaeghere, T., Singh, P., Lefever, E., Birkholz, J., 2024. Exploring Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis Methodologies for Literary-Historical Research Purposes, in: Sprugnoli, R., Passarotti, M. (Eds.), Proceedings of the Third Workshop on Language Technologies for Historical and Ancient Languages (LT4HALA) @ LREC-COLING-2024. ELRA and ICCL, Torino, Italia, pp. 129–143.

Klie, J.-C., Bugert, M., Boullosa, B., de Castilho, R.E., Gurevych, I., 2018. The INCEpTION Platform: Machine-Assisted and Knowledge-Oriented Interactive Annotation, in: Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Computational Linguistics: System Demonstrations. Association for Computational Linguistics, Santa Fe, USA, pp. 5–9.

NameTag 1

Quick description	NLP
Task it solves	extraction of flat named entities
Method it uses for that task	Named-Entity Recognition
Features (text enrichment)	named-entity labels
Metric	
Formalism	
Tagset	depending on language model

What can this tool do for you?

This tool marks named entities in your texts. You can easily supply to it your own NER model in any language.

Which languages can it work with (as of February 2023)?

This list presents currently available language models. Your own model can be for any language.

Language	Variety (geographical, or temporal if not modern)
Czech	
English	

Technical details

Version	1.2.0
Version Date:	February 2023 (maintenance version of a release from 2021-04-21)
Works on Operating Systems:	Linux
License:	Fully free (Mozilla Public License 2.0)
Distribution:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">webservice (http://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/nametag/);code https://github.com/ufal/nametag/releases/tag/v1.2.0
Download, installation, documentation, user guides:	http://hdl.handle.net/11858/00-097C-0000-0023-43CE-E https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/nametag/2 https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/nametag/ https://github.com/ufal/nametag/releases/tag/v2.0.0
User interface:	web GUI, REST API
Docker instance:	no
How does the tool process your text:	The tool detects and marks named entities.

Tool exports results:	
Statistical models:	This tool is not a statistical model / a set of statistical models, but it does include statistical models.
Plug in your own model:	You can easily train your statistical model to plug in this tool.
XML-TEI compatibility:	The tool produces XML tags but does not support XML-TEI input.
Required data input format:	plain text, vertical, conll-u

Which other tools from this list does this tool integrate?

NameTag1 models

Recommended tutorials

- <https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/nametag/1/tutorials> (in Czech)
- https://github.com/ufal/nametag/blob/master/bindings/python/examples/run_ner_simple.py

Related papers

Straková, J., Straka, M., & Hajič, J. (2014). Open-Source Tools for Morphology, Lemmatization, POS Tagging and Named Entity Recognition. *Proceedings of 52nd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics: System Demonstrations*, 13–18.

<http://www.aclweb.org/anthology/P/P14/P14-5003.pdf>

NameTag1 Models

Quick description	NLP
Task it solves	identify and mark named entities in texts
Method it uses for that task	Named-entity recognition – machine learning
Features (text enrichment)	named-entity labels
Metric	
Formalism	dependent on language model
Tagset	dependent on language model

What can this tool do for you?

These are models to plug in the NameTag2 named-entity recognizer.

Which languages can it work with (as of February 2023)?

Language	Variety (geographical, or temporal if not modern)
Czech	
English	

Technical details

Version	
Version Date:	2014
Works on Operating Systems:	
License:	Fully free (CC-BY-NC-SA 4.0)
Distribution:	zipped files from the LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ repository
Download, installation, documentation, user guides:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">English Model (CoNLL-2003) for NameTag: http://hdl.handle.net/11234/1-3118Czech Models (CNEC) for NameTag: http://hdl.handle.net/11858/00-097C-0000-0023-7D42-8
User interface:	None
Docker instance:	No
How does the tool process your text:	It gives the named-entity recognizer the know-how of named-entity annotation in a given language, according to a given tagset.
Tool exports results:	No
Statistical models:	This tool is a statistical model / a set of statistical models.
XML-TEI compatibility:	This tool does not support XML-TEI at all.

Required data input format:	None
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Related papers

Straková, J., Straka, M., & Hajič, J. (2014). Open-Source Tools for Morphology, Lemmatizations POS Tagging and Named Entity Recognition. *Proceedings of 52nd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics: System Demonstrations*, 13–18.

<http://www.aclweb.org/anthology/P/P14/P14-5003.pdf>

NameTag 2

Quick description	NLP
Task it solves	extraction of named entities, even nested
Method it uses for that task	Named-Entity Recognition
Features (text enrichment)	named-entity labels, also nested
Metric	
Formalism	
Tagset	depending on language model

What can this tool do for you?

This tool marks named entities in your texts. When named entities are nested, it recognizes the nestings. For instance, two entities can be recognized in *Humboldt University*: institution (the whole string) and surname (*Humboldt*).

Which languages can it work with (as of February 2023)?

This list presents currently available language models.

Language	Variety (geographical, or temporal if not modern)
Czech	
Dutch	
English	
German	
Spanish	
Ukrainian	

Technical details

Version	2.0.0
Version Date:	2021-04-21
Works on Operating Systems:	Linux
License:	Fully free (Mozilla Public License 2.0)
Distribution:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• webservice (http://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/nametag/);• code to run your own NameTag server• commandline tool at https://github.com/ufal/nametag/releases/tag/v2.0.0
Download, installation, documentation, user guides:	http://hdl.handle.net/11858/00-097C-0000-0023-43CE-E https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/nametag/2 https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/nametag/ https://github.com/ufal/nametag/releases/tag/v2.0.0
User interface:	web GUI, REST API

Docker instance:	no
How does the tool process your text:	The tool detects and marks named entities.
Tool exports results:	
Statistical models:	This tool is (not) a statistical model / a set of statistical models, and/ but it does (not) include statistical models.
Plug in your own model:	You can(not) easily train your statistical model to plug in this tool.
XML-TEI compatibility:	The tool produces XML tags but does not support XML-TEI input.
Required data input format:	plain text, vertical, conll-u

Which other tools from this list does this tool integrate?

NameTag2 models

Related papers

Straková, J., Straka, M., & Hajič, J. (2019). Neural Architectures for Nested NER through Linearization. Proceedings of the 57th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, 5326–5331.

NameTag2 Models

Quick description	NLP
Task it solves	identify and mark named entities in texts
Method it uses for that task	Named-entity recognition – machine learning
Features (text enrichment)	named-entity labels
Metric	
Formalism	dependent on language model
Tagset	dependent on language model

What can this tool do for you?

These are models to plug in the NameTag2 named-entity recognizer.

Which languages can it work with (as of February 2023)?

Language	Variety (geographical, or temporal if not modern)
Czech	
Dutch	
English	
German	
Spanish	
Ukrainian	

Technical details

Version	
Version Date:	
Works on Operating Systems:	
License:	Fully free (CC-BY-NC-SA 4.0)
Distribution:	zipped files from the LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ repository
Download, installation, documentation, user guides:	https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/nametag/2/models https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/repository/xmlui/handle/11234/1-3773
User interface:	None
Docker instance:	No
How does the tool process your text:	It gives the named-entity recognizer the know-how of named-entity annotation in a given language, according to a given tagset.
Tool exports results:	
Statistical models:	This tool is a statistical model / a set of statistical models.

XML-TEI compatibility:	This tool does not support XML-TEI at all.
Required data input format:	None

Related papers

Straková, J., Straka, M., & Hajič, J. (2019). Neural Architectures for Nested NER through Linearization. Proceedings of the 57th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, 5326–5331.

NameTag2 Models

Quick description	NLP
Task it solves	identify and mark named entities in texts
Method it uses for that task	Named-entity recognition – machine learning
Features (text enrichment)	named-entity labels
Metric	
Formalism	dependent on language model
Tagset	dependent on language model

What can this tool do for you?

These are models to plug in the NameTag2 named-entity recognizer.

Which languages can it work with (as of February 2023)?

Language	Variety (geographical, or temporal if not modern)
Czech	
Dutch	
English	
German	
Spanish	
Ukrainian	

Technical details

Version	
Version Date:	
Works on Operating Systems:	
License:	Fully free (CC-BY-NC-SA 4.0)
Distribution:	zipped files from the LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ repository
Download, installation, documentation, user guides:	https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/nametag/2/models https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/repository/xmlui/handle/11234/1-3773
User interface:	None
Docker instance:	No
How does the tool process your text:	It gives the named-entity recognizer the know-how of named-entity annotation in a given language, according to a given tagset.
Tool exports results:	
Statistical models:	This tool is a statistical model / a set of statistical models.

XML-TEI compatibility:	This tool does not support XML-TEI at all.
Required data input format:	None

Related papers

Straková, J., Straka, M., & Hajič, J. (2019). Neural Architectures for Nested NER through Linearization. Proceedings of the 57th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, 5326–5331.

NameTag 3

Quick description	NLP
Task it solves	extraction of named entities, even nested for Czech or custom trained models that provide nesting information
Method it uses for that task	Named-Entity Recognition
Features (text enrichment)	named-entity labels, also nested for Czech
Metric	
Formalism	
Tagset	PER, ORG, LOC, MISC

What can this tool do for you?

This tool marks named entities in your texts. When Czech named entities are nested, it recognizes the nestings. For instance, two entities can be recognized in *Humboldt University*: institution (the whole string) and surname (*Humboldt*).

Which languages can it work with (as of February 2024)?

The currently available models are Czech and “multilingual”. The multilingual model is trained on CoNLL data of the following languages

Language	Variety (geographical, or temporal if not modern)
Czech	
Dutch	
English	
German	
Spanish	
Ukrainian	

Technical details

Version	240830
Version Date:	2024-10
Works on Operating Systems:	all
License:	Models: CC BY-NC-SA, tool itself: Mozilla Public License 2.0 ,
Distribution:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• webservice (http://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/nametag/);• code to run your own NameTag server• commandline tool at https://github.com/ufal/nametag/releases/tag/v2.0.0
Download, installation, documentation, user	http://hdl.handle.net/11858/00-097C-0000-0023-43CE-E https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/nametag/2 https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/nametag/

guides:	https://github.com/ufal/nametag/releases/tag/v2.0.0
User interface:	web GUI, REST API, Python
Docker instance:	no
How does the tool process your text:	The tool detects and marks named entities.
Tool exports results:	
Statistical models:	This tool is not a statistical model / a set of statistical models, but it does include statistical models.
Plug in your own model:	You can easily train your statistical model to plug in this tool.
XML-TEI compatibility:	The tool produces XML tags but does not support XML-TEI input.
Required data input format:	plain text, vertical, conll-u

Which other tools from this list does this tool integrate?

NameTag3 models

Related papers

Straková, J., Straka, M., & Hajič, J. (2019). Neural Architectures for Nested NER through Linearization. Proceedings of the 57th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, 5326–5331.

NameTag3 Models

Quick description	NLP
Task it solves	identify and mark named entities in texts
Method it uses for that task	Named-entity recognition – machine learning
Features (text enrichment)	named-entity labels
Metric	
Formalism	dependent on language model
Tagset	dependent on language model

What can this tool do for you?

These are models to plug in the NameTag2 named-entity recognizer.

Which languages can it work with (as of February 2023)?

Language	Variety (geographical, or temporal if not modern)
Czech	
multilingual	Trained on Dutch, English, German, Spanish, Ukrainian

Technical details

Version	240830
Version Date:	2024-08-30
Works on Operating Systems:	all
License:	Fully free (CC-BY-NC-SA 4.0)
Distribution:	zipped files from the LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ repository
Download, installation, documentation, user guides:	https://ufal.mff.cuni.cz/nametag/3/models https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/repository/xmlui/handle/11234/1-5678
User interface:	None
Docker instance:	No
How does the tool process your text:	It gives the named-entity recognizer the know-how of named-entity annotation in a given language, according to a given tagset.
Tool exports results:	
Statistical models:	This tool is a statistical model / a set of statistical models.
XML-TEI compatibility:	This tool does not support XML-TEI at all.
Required data input format:	None

Related papers

Straková, J., Straka, M., & Hajič, J. (2019). Neural Architectures for Nested NER through Linearization. Proceedings of the 57th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, 5326–5331.

Cadet

Which Operating Systems does it work on?

- Windows
- Unix
- MacOS
- Linux

License

- Fully free (GNU General Public License v3.0)

Distribution

- Web application
- Jupyter Notebook

Where to download, how to install, documentation, user guides

- <https://github.com/BCDH/cadet>

User interface

- GUI
- Jupyter Notebooks

Docker instance

- No, but we provide a Dockerfile (<https://github.com/BCDH/cadet/blob/master/Dockerfile>) that can be used to build an image

How does the tool process your text?

- Makes the collection and processing of language assets accessible to humanists without a background in programming or data science.
- Allows users to tailor language data to their specific needs and research domains.
- Streamlines the process of creating and processing language assets for new spaCy language models
- Automatically adds some labels (annotation) to your texts.
- Allows you to manually annotate your texts.
- Returns some metrics as numbers or tables.
- Returns some visualization (plots, interactive elements, etc.).

Does the tool allow you to export the results?

- Yes

Is this tool a statistical model (or a set thereof)?

- No

Can you easily train and use your own statistical model with this tool?

- No, but you can create a new spaCy model based on the language assets you have processed with this tool.

XML-TEI compatibility

- None.

How is an input document to be structured for the tool?

Plain text.

Methods and features

We use a tool to solve a task. The tool is approaching this task with methods to provide some features or compute values of some metrics for the given text. Features typically enrich the input text (either in-line or stand-off) with labels or filter the text according to a query. Assigned labels typically belong to a given tagset (e. g. Universal Dependencies or Penn Treebank) or/and pertain to a formalism such as HPSG or minimalist syntax). Filters typically pertain to a query language (also a formalism).

Quick orientation for contributors	Task (what you want to achieve with that method)	Method (usually more generic than task)	Features/ Metric/ Formalism, Tagset
Project management	Set up a space online for creating and editing projects	User management	web platform
Project management	Organise your languages/projects in one place	Project and language management	web platform
Simplified no-code	Create a spaCy	Automated build	

interface to NLP tools	language object	steps	
Simplified no-code interface to NLP tools	Tokenize	GUI for auditing tokenization	
Simplified no-code interface to NLP tools	Lookups & matching	Rule-based lemmatization, POS-tagging and NER	Penn Treebank Part-of-Speech Tag Set, NER Tagset
Annotation	Preparation of raw textual material	Corpus preparation	Universal Dependencies label scheme,
Annotation	Efficient bulk token annotation	Manual text annotation/annotation editing	Annotation of tokens by token frequency
Project management	Export preprocessed data and set up a spaCy language object		conllu, spacy-model

Which human languages does the tool support (as of February 2023)?

Language	Variety (geographical, or temporal if not modern)
Any (it is language-agnostic)	

Which other tools from this list does it integrate?

- None.

What can this tool do for you?

Cadet allows you to create and generate new language models for spaCy. spaCy supports many languages, but not all, and Cadet helps you create a new language object and associate various assets with it, including sample sentences, tokenization rules, lemma lookup tables,

stop words etc. It includes a batch annotation feature which allows you to annotate the most frequent tokens in your corpus quickly before exporting the corpus for more detailed annotation work in Inception. Once you have annotated your text corpus and are ready to train your model, Cadet will help you load and pre-process your data so that you can do your model training and packaging with spaCy.